

EFFECT OF SiC REINFORCEMENT ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SiC/Al METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY : Volume fraction of SiC particles in SiCp/2124Al composite was varied from 10 to 30 vol% and extrusion ratio of 20 vol% SiCw/2124Al was varied from 12:1 to 70:1 to investigate the effects of volume fraction, aspect ratio and misorientation angle of reinforcements on mechanical properties of SiC/2124Al composites. A new concept of effective aspect ratio was proposed, combining the effects of aspect ratio and alignment of reinforcement, as a new parameter indicating the load transfer efficiency of misaligned reinforcement in metal matrix composite. The elastic modulus of SiCp/2124Al composite increased with increasing the volume fraction of SiC particles in 2124Al matrix. The anisotropy in elastic modulus of SiCw/2124Al composite increased with increasing the extrusion ratio of consolidated SiCw/2124Al billet. The magnitude and anisotropy of yield strength of SiC/2124Al composite could be estimated more accurately by substituting the average aspect ratio by effective aspect ratio in the shear-lag model.

KEYWORDS: metal matrix composite, silicon carbide, mechanical properties, yield strength, elastic modulus, load transfer, anisotropy

INTRODUCTION

Discontinuous silicon carbide reinforced aluminum matrix composites have received considerable interest due to excellent mechanical properties and reasonable cost for fabrication process[1-4]. The addition of ceramic reinforcements in metal matrix results in a marked improvement in mechanical properties, such as tensile strength, elastic modulus and creep resistance[5,6]. The strengthening mechanism of metal matrix composite based on the load transfer from metal matrix to reinforcement has been formulated by the shear-lag model[7,8]. There exists an anisotropy in mechanical properties of metal matrix composite, which is originated from the directional alignment of reinforcement resulted from secondary deformation process such as rolling or extrusion. However, the shear-lag model gives poor estimation of anisotropy on mechanical properties in case of the short fiber or whisker reinforced metal matrix composites[9]. For example, the modified shear-lag model by Nardone and Prewo overestimates the strength in longitudinal direction and underestimates

the strength in transverse direction, which is caused from the assumption of perfect alignment of reinforcement[10].

In this paper, we have suggested a new concept of effective aspect ratios for spherical particles and misaligned cylindrical whiskers to analyze the load transfer efficiency of reinforcement in metal matrix considering volume fraction, aspect ratio and misorientation angle of reinforcement. The effects of volume fraction of SiC particles in SiCp/2124Al and extrusion ratio of SiCw/2124Al on mechanical properties, such as elastic modulus and yield strength, were analyzed based on comparison between the experimental results on mechanical properties and theoretical values based on the shear-lag model.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The SiC/2124Al metal matrix composites were fabricated by powder metallurgy process by mixing atomized 2124Al powders with average diameter of 20 μ m and α -SiC particles with average diameter of 8 μ m or β -SiC whiskers with average diameter of 1.5 μ m and average length of 50~60 μ m. The SiC reinforcements and 2124Al powders were wet mixed in ethanol under ultrasonic stirring condition. The mixtures were dried and consolidated into cylindrical ingots by hot pressing at 570 $^{\circ}$ C with a pressure of 90MPa under 1×10^{-5} Torr. The consolidated ingots were hot extruded at 500 $^{\circ}$ C with an extrusion ratios of 12:1 to 70:1, then the extruded bars were solution heat treated at 493 $^{\circ}$ C for 3hrs and followed by aging at 192 $^{\circ}$ C for 8hrs. The microstructures of SiC/2124Al composites were observed using an optical microscopy. The aspect ratios of SiC whiskers in metal matrix composite were measured from the scanning electron micrographs after etching in 10% NaOH solution. The elastic moduli of SiC/2124Al metal matrix composites were obtained from resonant ultrasonic spectroscopy, and yield strengths at room temperature were measured using the Instron under a strain rate of 1.33×10^{-3} /s.

THEORETICAL MODELING

Load Transfer from Matrix to a Cylindrical Misaligned Whisker

A differential longitudinal tensile stress, $d\sigma_{f,l}$, balances with a longitudinal shear stress, $\tau_{i,l}$, on the side surface of thin slice cut perpendicular to the longitudinal direction of a cylindrical misaligned whisker with length of $2L$ and diameter of $2r$ in metal matrix composite, as shown in Fig.1(a). Then a differential equation can be derived from the force equilibrium between the longitudinal stresses on a whisker as following Eq.(1).

$$-d\sigma_{f,l} = \frac{2\tau_{i,l}}{r} dx \quad (1)$$

When misorientation angle of whisker is θ and stress transferred from matrix to the end surface of whisker is σ_m , an integration of Eq.(1) using a boundary condition, $\sigma_{f,l} = \sigma_m \cos \theta$ at $x = L$, gives a solution of longitudinal tensile stress, $\sigma_{f,l}$, along the longitudinal direction of a whisker as following Eq.(2).

$$\sigma_{f,l} = \sigma_m \cos \theta + \frac{2\tau_{i,l}(L-x)}{r} \quad (2)$$

It is reasonable to assume that the longitudinal shear stress at the end surface of whisker is one half of the tensile stress along the longitudinal direction, i.e. $\tau_i = \sigma_i \cos \theta / 2$. Then the average tensile stress, $\bar{\sigma}_{f,l}$, in longitudinal direction of a misaligned whisker is expressed as,

$$\bar{\sigma}_{f,l} = \sigma_m \cos \theta + S \cdot \frac{\sigma_m \cos \theta}{2} \quad (3)$$

where S is aspect ratio of whisker, which is defined as L/r .

On the other hand, a differential transverse tensile stress, $d\sigma_{f,t}$, balances with a transverse stress, $\tau_{i,t}$, on the side surface of thin slice cut perpendicular to the transverse direction of a cylindrical misaligned whisker as shown in Fig.1(b). Then a differential equation can be also derived from the force equilibrium between the transverse stresses on a whisker as Eq.(4),

$$4Lr \cos^2 \phi (\tau_{i,t} + r\tau_{i,t}) d\phi = -d\sigma_{f,t} 4Lr \cos \phi \quad (4)$$

where $\tau_{i,t}$ is transverse shear stress on side surface of thin slice of whisker and ϕ is the angle geometrically defined in Fig.1(b). The differential transverse tensile stress can be expressed as,

$$-d\sigma_{f,t} = \left(\cos \phi + \frac{r}{L} \cos^2 \phi \right) \cdot \tau_{i,t} \cdot d\phi \quad (5)$$

The integration of Eq.(5) using a boundary condition, $\sigma_{f,t} = \sigma_m \sin \theta$ at $\phi=90^\circ$, gives a following solution of transverse tensile stress, $\sigma_{f,t}$, along the transverse direction of a whisker,

$$\sigma_{f,t} = \sigma_m \sin \theta + \left[\frac{(r-y)}{L} - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{y}{r} \right) + \frac{\pi}{2} \right] \tau_{i,t} \quad (6)$$

where y is the radial distance of a thin slice from the center of whisker along the line AA' in Fig.1(b). Since the radial distance, y , is represented as $r \sin \phi$ and dy is substituted by $r \cos \phi d\phi$, the average transverse tensile stress acting on a whisker can be formulated as Eq.(7),

$$\bar{\sigma}_{f,t} = \frac{\int_0^{90} \sigma_{f,t} \cdot 4Lr \cos \phi r \cos \phi d\phi}{\int_0^{90} 4Lr \cos \phi r \cos \phi d\phi} = \sigma_m \cdot \sin \theta + \left(\frac{3\pi - 4}{3\pi} + \frac{\pi}{8S} \right) \cdot \tau_{i,t} \quad (7)$$

Assuming $\tau_{i,t} = \sigma_m \sin \theta / 2$, the Eq.(7) can be expressed as following Eq.(8).

Fig. 1: Schematic diagrams showing (a) stress components on thin slice cut perpendicular to longitudinal direction and (b) stress components on thin slice cut perpendicular to transverse direction of a cylindrical whisker misaligned with angle θ from the loading axis.

$$\bar{\sigma}_{f,t} = \sigma_m \sin \theta + \left[\frac{4 - \pi^2}{4\pi} + \left(1 - \frac{4}{3\pi}\right) \frac{1}{S} \right] \frac{\sigma_m \sin \theta}{2} \quad (8)$$

The stress transferred on a whisker along the loading axis, $\bar{\sigma}_f$, can be calculated by vector summation of average longitudinal stress and average transverse stress as follows.

$$\bar{\sigma}_f = \bar{\sigma}_{f,l} \cdot \cos \theta + \bar{\sigma}_{f,t} \cdot \sin \theta = \sigma_m \left[1 + \frac{S}{2} \cos^2 \theta + \left(\frac{3\pi - 4}{3\pi} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{S} \right) \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{2} \right] \quad (9)$$

By using the rule-of-mixture, the strength of metal matrix composite with misaligned whiskers is calculated as following Eq.(10),

$$\sigma = V_f \bar{\sigma}_f + V_m \bar{\sigma}_m = \frac{V_f \sigma_m}{2} \left[S \cos^2 \theta + \left(\frac{3\pi - 4}{3\pi} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{S} \right) \sin^2 \theta \right] + \sigma_m \quad (10)$$

where V_f and V_m are volume fraction of whisker and matrix, respectively.

The difference between the strength of composites with misaligned whisker and that with perfect aligned whisker can be analyzed by comparing Eq.(10) with conventional shear lag model as following Eq.(11). The average aspect ratio of a whisker, S , is changed to a function of aspect ratio and misorientation angle in Eq.(11). Comparing Eq.(10) and Eq.(11), a new parameter named effective aspect ratio, S_{eff} , of a misaligned whisker is defined as following Eq.(12).

$$\sigma = \frac{V_f \sigma_m}{2} S + \sigma_m \quad (11)$$

$$S_{eff} = S \cos^2 \theta + \left(\frac{3\pi - 4}{3\pi} \right) \left(1 + \frac{1}{S} \right) \sin^2 \theta \quad (12)$$

Load Transfer from Matrix to a Spherical Particle

Fig.2 shows the stresses acting on a spherical particulate reinforcement in metal matrix composite. The differential normal stress, $d\sigma_p$, should balance with the shear stress on side surface of a thin slice cut perpendicular to the loading axis. A differential equation based on the force equilibrium between normal stress and shear stress is derived as Eq.(13) and can be simplified into Eq.(14),

$$-d\sigma_p \pi r^2 \cos^2 \phi = 2\pi r \cos \phi r d\phi \cdot \tau_i \cos^2 \phi \quad (13)$$

$$-d\sigma_p = 2 \cos \phi \cdot \tau_i \cdot d\phi \quad (14)$$

where σ_p is normal stress on a particle and τ_i is shear stress at interface. When the stress transferred from matrix to the end surface of a particle is σ_m , the normal stress perpendicular to the thin slice, σ_p , is calculated as Eq.(15) by integrating the Eq.(14) with a boundary condition of $\sigma_p = \sigma_m$ at $\phi = 90^\circ$.

$$\sigma_p = \sigma_m + (1 - \sin \phi) 2\tau_i \quad (15)$$

Then, the average normal stress on a spherical particle is calculated as following Eq.(16).

$$\bar{\sigma}_p = \frac{\int_0^{90} \sigma_p \pi r^2 \cos^2 \phi \cdot r \cos \phi d\phi}{\int_0^{90} \pi r^2 \cos^2 \phi \cdot r \cos \phi d\phi} = \sigma_m + \frac{5}{4} \tau_i \quad (16)$$

Assuming the shear stress at interface is one half of the stress on matrix, i.e. $\tau_i = \sigma_m / 2$, the strength of particle reinforced composite is estimated by the rule of mixture of the average normal stress on a particle, $\bar{\sigma}_p$, and the stress on matrix, σ_m , expressed as Eq.(17).

$$\sigma_p = V_p \cdot \left(\sigma_m + \frac{5}{4} \tau_m \right) + V_m \sigma_m = V_p \sigma_m \left(\frac{1.25}{2} \right) + \sigma_m \quad (17)$$

By comparing the Eq.(17) with the shear-lag model expressed in Eq.(11), the effective aspect ratio of a spherical particle is calculated to be a constant of 1.25.

Fig.2 : Schematic diagram showing stress components acting on spherical particle.

Fig. 3 : The orientation distribution of SiC whiskers in 20 vol.% SiCw/2124Al composite extruded with a ratio of 25:1.

Effective Aspect Ratio of Distributed Misaligned Whiskers

The whiskers in extruded metal matrix composites are not perfectly aligned parallel to the extrusion axis, instead, they have certain distribution of misorientation angles from the extrusion direction as shown in Fig.3. An exponential function was adopted as probability density function of misorientation distribution as following Eq.(18),

$$F(\theta) = A \exp(-K\theta) \quad (18)$$

where A is constant, K is parameter depending on the degree of alignment, and θ is misorientation angle. Then, the effective aspect ratio along longitudinal direction, $S_{eff,l}$, can be calculated by integrating $S_{eff}(\theta)F(\theta)2\pi\sin\theta$ over the whole hemisphere from $\theta=0$ to $\theta=\pi/2$ as follows,

$$S_{eff,l} = \int_0^{\pi/2} S_{eff}(\theta)F(\theta)(2\pi \sin \theta)d\theta \quad (19)$$

where $S_{eff}(\theta)$ is effective aspect ratio of a whisker with misorientation angle θ , $F(\theta)$ is probability function of misorientation angle θ and $2\pi\sin\theta d\theta$ is an area of shaded strip in Fig.4(a). The effective aspect ratio along transverse direction, $S_{eff,t}$, can be calculated by similar procedure with geometrical consideration. Fig.4(b) shows a whisker misaligned by angle η from the transverse axis of extrusion and misaligned by angle θ from the extrusion axis. The three angles, η, ϕ and θ , shown in Fig.4(b) have geometrical relationship as follows.

$$\theta = \cos^{-1}(\sin \eta \cos \phi) \quad (20)$$

Fig. 4 : Schematic diagram showing hemisphere of composite for the calculation of effective aspect ratio along (a) longitudinal direction and (b) transverse direction in metal matrix composite reinforced with distributed misaligned whiskers.

Then, the effective aspect ratio along transverse direction can be calculated as follows,

$$S_{\text{eff},t} = 4 \int_0^{\pi/2} \int_0^{\pi/2} S_{\text{eff}}(\eta) F[\cos^{-1}(\sin \eta \cos \phi)] \sin \eta d\eta d\phi \quad (21)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The typical microstructures of SiCp/2124Al composites with different volume fraction of SiC particulate reinforcement are shown in Fig. 3. The distribution of the SiC particles within Al matrix is fairly homogeneous. Fig.6(a) shows the variation of effective aspect ratio of whiskers along longitudinal and transverse directions with varying the constant K when the average aspect ratio is assumed as 4. The effective aspect ratio along longitudinal direction increases, while the effective aspect ratio along transverse direction decreases with increasing the constant K. When K is 0 for randomly distributed whiskers, the effective aspect ratios are identical in longitudinal and transverse directions. The effective aspect ratio of SiC whiskers was sensitively dependent on the degree of alignment in addition to the aspect ratio in extruded MMCs.

The calculated ratio of yield strength in longitudinal direction to that transverse direction was shown in Fig.6(b) with varying the constant K for the composite with volume fraction, V_f , of 0.2 and average aspect ratio, S, of 4.

Fig.5 : The optical micrographs of SiCp/Al metal matrix composites with different volume fractions of SiC particles. (a) 10 vol% SiCp/2124Al, (b) 20 vol% SiCp/2124Al, (c) 30 vol% SiCp/2124Al.

Fig. 6 : (a) The variation of the effective aspect ratio of distributed whiskers along longitudinal and transverse directions with varying the degree of alignment, K , and (b) the variation of the ratio of yield strength in longitudinal direction to that in transverse direction with varying the degree of alignment, K , when the average aspect ratio is 4.

The yield strength in longitudinal direction shows 20% higher than that in transverse direction when K is 4. The anisotropy in yield strength increases with increasing K as shown in Fig.6(b). The yield strength of metal matrix composite can be more accurately represented by substituting the effective aspect ratio, S_{eff} , for the average aspect ratio, S , in the shear-lag model proposed by Nardone and Prewo[9]. The ratio of yield strength in longitudinal direction to that of transverse direction is calculated as follows,

$$\frac{\sigma_l}{\sigma_t} = \frac{V_f (S_{eff,l} / 2 + 1) + V_m}{V_f (S_{eff,t} / 2 + 1) + V_m} \quad (22)$$

Fig. 7(a) shows elastic modulus of SiCp/2124Al composite with increasing volume fraction of SiC particles. The elastic moduli along longitudinal and transverse directions increased with increasing volume fraction of SiC particles. The elastic modulus of SiCp/2124Al lies between upper bound and lower bound of calculated rule-of-mixture. Fig. 7(b) shows the anisotropy of elastic modulus of 20vol% SiCp/2124Al and 20vol% SiCw/2124Al with increasing extrusion ratio from 12:1 to 70:1. The anisotropy of elastic modulus increased with increasing extrusion ratio because degree of misorientation of reinforcement decreased. The anisotropy of elastic modulus of SiCw/2124Al is larger than that of SiCp/2124Al because of the larger average aspect ratio of SiCw.

Table 1 compares the measured yield strengths in longitudinal and transverse directions with the estimated yield strengths of SiCw/Al composite based on the shear-lag model by Nardone and Prewo[9] and our modified shear-lag model. Nardone and Prewo assumed that the average aspect ratio is 4 along longitudinal direction and 1 along transverse direction. The shear-lag model generally overestimates the longitudinal yield strength and underestimates the transverse yield strength due to the assumption of perfect alignment. However, the modification of the shear-lag model substituted by the effective aspect ratio gives the estimated yield strength more close to the measured yield strength.

Fig. 7: (a) The variation of elastic modulus of SiCp/2124Al with increasing the volume fraction of SiC particles and (b) the variation of elastic anisotropy(E_{11}/E_{22}) of SiCp/2124Al and SiCw/2124Al with increasing the extrusion ratio.

Table 1: The comparison of estimated yield strengths along longitudinal and transverse directions of extruded 20vol.% SiCw/Al composite.

Direction	Yield Strength		
	Measured	Estimated based on Effective Aspect Ratio	Estimated based on Average Aspect Ratio
Longitudinal	524 MPa	520 MPa	551 MPa
Transverse	466 MPa	436 MPa	433 MPa
Anisotropy	1.12	1.19	1.27

CONCLUSIONS

The load transfer efficiencies of distributed misaligned reinforcements in metal matrix composites were formulated by suggesting a new parameter named effective aspect ratio, which is a function of aspect ratio and misorientation angle. The increase in average aspect ratio and degree of alignment resulted in an increased load transfer efficiency of a cylindrical whisker, while the load transfer efficiency of a spherical particle is identical independent of direction. The effect of distribution of misorientation of whisker on strength anisotropy was calculated. New shear-lag model using effective aspect ratio gave more accurate estimation of yield strength and strength anisotropy than the conventional shear lag model assuming perfect alignment of whisker.

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